

Update on MICRODEM in DEMIX

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Abstract—MICRODEM has been used for almost all the data manipulation and statistical computations in DEMIX. Continued work seeks to improve and extend the computations, and compare DEMs. The original landmark DEMs: SRTM, ASTER, and NASADEM should now be retired since Copernicus DEM now clearly outperforms them .

I. INTRODUCTION

While the JRC Technical Report (Bielski and others, in press) was in preparation (group work ended at the end of summer 2023), [multiple preprint versions of the paper on the DEMIX wine contest were posted](#). The JRC Technical Report will contain significant coverage of the paper published in February 2024 with 12 authors [1]. In September 2024 6 of that paper’s authors, including 5 of the 10 authors of the JRC technical report, published a follow-on paper [2] which was started after preparation of the JRC report and final writing of the earlier paper [1]. This paper discusses work in MICRODEM since work on the JRC Technical Paper was completed. Essentially all of the analysis for the DEMIX comparisons in both papers was done in MICRODEM [3,4].

II. ENHANCED DEMIX DATA AND METHODOLOGY

The second paper [2] significantly improved the methodology of the first [1]. Figure 1, the paper’s abstract, highlights the changes:

- Included 124 test areas and 3462 DEMIX tiles, an order of magnitude increase. Of most interest, this allows creation of figures like those in section 4 of this paper.
- Considered 4 additional global DEMs: DSM [TanDEM-X](#), and DTMs [CoastalDEM](#), [DiluviumDEM](#), and [DeltaDTM](#). Of the total of 10 test DEMs considered, 4 are edited DTMs.

- Used 16 different derived land surface parameters (LSPs) in addition to elevation to compare grids. This compares to 2 LSPs plus elevation used in [1], where the 5 criteria for each LSP are highly correlated and not independent. The new DEMIX GIS database [5] includes the original 15 criteria for anyone who still wants to use them.
- Introduced fraction of unexplained variance (FUV), ranging from 0 (best) to 1 (worst), as a better criterion than the statistics of the difference distribution. This allows directly comparing different criteria, and compares the criteria in terms of correspondence with the reference DEMs. The evaluations from the difference distributions [1] have different ranges in different test areas and for the different criteria, making comparisons difficult.
- Used 2 geomorphometric classifications of every pixel, also with a range from 0 to 1.
- Expanded the channel network criterion to the entire data set, also with a range from 0 to 1.
- Used evaluations rather than rankings as a better way to show differences among global DEMs, decreasing the effects of having to set a tolerance for ties.
- Due to the severe challenges of applying subjective criteria at scale to hundreds or thousands of test tiles, the rationale for the wine contest statistics becomes murky. This was not explicitly stated, but is clear from the modified methodology adopted which does not have to deal with the complexity added with subjective criteria.

Based on their limited utility, [2] did not do some of the analysis in the first paper [1]:

- Compare to reference DSMs, which are available only for a limited number of test areas. Because the test DEMs are in many cases perform better than the edited DTMs, even

Guth, P.L.

when compared with a reference DTM, this is not a significant limitation.

- Compute per-pixel land type statistics. Breaking down the results by characteristics of the tile proves more useful, as shown in the diagram in the lower right corner of Figure 1. This only becomes feasible with the much larger number of tiles.
- Publish any Friedman statistics which they found less useful than other metrics and graphics.

III. NEW PUBLISHED DEMIX RESULTS

Key results from [2]:

- [CopDEM](#) generally remains the best DEM, even when compared to a reference DTM or the edited derivatives of CopDEM to produce a DTM.
- [ALOS DEM \(AW3D30\)](#) is slightly better than CopDEM in very steep terrain.
- Edited DTMs ([FABDEM](#), [CoastalDEM](#), [DiluviumDEM](#), and [DeltaDTM](#)) generally improve slightly on elevation metrics compared to CopDEM, but are worse for many derived LSPs because they were only trained for elevation to remove vegetation and they can hallucinate.
- None of the global DEMs, even the edited ones designed for low elevation coastal areas, perform well in areas with average slopes under 5%.
- Strongly implied that NASADEM makes few changes to SRTM, and that NASADEM, SRTM, and ASTER should be retired. Results for these were included in the new data base [5], but excluded from much of the analysis to concentrate of the DEMs that are reasonable choices to use.
- LSPs can be ranked in terms of their FUV and the sensitivity of the LSPs to DEM quality; curvature measures are hardest for global DEMs to match to the reference.
- Edited DTMs can hallucinate,

IV. WORK IN PROGRESS WITH NEW 1 ARCSEC DTMS

Several new one second global DEMs have appeared ([FathomDEM](#), [EDTM](#), and [GEDTM](#)), and the MICRODEM DEMIX analysis has been adapted to them (Figure 2). Preliminary work suggests very high quality for FathomDEM.

V. WORK IN PROGRESS WITH NEW 0.15 ARCSEC DTMS

Guth and Herrera-Cruz have a paper at Geomorphometry 2025 on developing a methodology to compare commercial 5 m DEMs to reference high resolution lidar DTMs. Particularly in urban areas, it is very hard to replace the buildings with a realistic ground surface. What the lidar cannot see, but the national mapping agency fills in to create the DTM, is not what the radar or optical sensors see from space (it's in fact not really there, but some approximation), and the comparison is problematical. The 5 m scale also proves very sensitive to slight variations in elevation within the window used for computing LSPs: relative accuracy can be more important than absolute elevation accuracy for many computations.

VI. IMPORTANCE OF THE PIXEL GEOMETRY MODEL

Previous DEMIX papers [1,6] stressed the importance GeoTIFF GTRasterTypeGeoKey (#1025). The addition of more DEMs requires a more nuanced pixel origin/geometry model, which is unambiguously encoded in GeoTIFF files in two tags, GTRasterTypeGeoKey (#1025) and ModelTiepointTag (#33922). The GTRasterTypeGeoKey has two values, pixel-is-point and pixel-is-area, but only defines how to interpret the area of the pixel, and does not refer to the sampling strategy for the pixel (even Landsat is coded by USGS as pixel-is-point). The two models were defined as SRTM and ALOS, for the first global DEMs to use each (Table 1).

Some software changes the GTRasterTypeGeoKey (#1025). When operating on a pixel-is-point DEM, Whitebox did not change tag #1025 when creating a slope map, GDAL changed the tag when creating a slope map, SAGA changed the tag when creating an aspect map, and QGIS changed the tag when rewriting the DEM. Those programs that changed tag #1025 also changed ModelTiepointTag (#33922) with a 1/2 pixel shift, so that all the grids retain the SRTM geometric model. I have talked to the author of another geomorphometry program and programmers for a commercial GIS, and we agree that internally the programs need to adopt a single model (if needed change tag #1025 and shift the coordinates in #33922 by 1/2 pixel), and that the pixel-is-point makes computations simplest; obviously other programs make a different choice.

CopDEM best compromise

Derived grids vary in quality

Moderate slope best for DEM quality

Figure 1. Graphical abstract [2]. Top row shows the data and methodology, and bottom row highlights the key results.

Figure 2. Comparing 6 global DEMs, 4 DTMs and 2 DSMs. This averages 9 criteria: elevation, hillshade, curvatures (plan, profile, and tangential), roughness, slope, and topographic position index.

Table 1. Pixel origin or geometric model for global 1” DEMs

DEMs	Geotiff Pixel is (tag #1025)	Model tie point (tag #33922)	DEM nominal corner contains	Pixel origin model
CopDEM, FABDEM, FathomDEM, SRTM, and NASADEM	Point	DEM nominal corner	Pixel centroid	SRTM
ASTER	Area	½ pixel offset from nominal corner	Pixel centroid	SRTM
ALOS, USGS 3DEP, Diluvium DEM, EDTM, GEDTM, Coastal DEM	Area	DEM nominal corner	Pixel corner	ALOS

If GTRasterTypeGeoKey (#1025) were to be defined to reflect the sampling underlying the data in the Geotiff (whether the elevations represent a point, or a pixel average), advocated by some workers, there are several significant issues that need to be resolved:

- Many legacy data sets did not use it that way, and they will be around for a long time, so that interpretations will be questionable. All global 1” sample a large area, and not the exact elevation at the point.
- Many software programs will have to be rewritten to avoid changing the tag.
- Having only two choices for the sampling for the grid is probably too simplistic. Which choice is appropriate for a slope grid? A filtered DEM? A drainage contributing area? A map algebra grid, say from shifting vertical datums?
- If the grid value is really from a point, but had to be assigned to the nearest grid node because the sampled points were not on the grid, how should tag #1025 be coded?
- Should there be a clean break, with a Geotiff tag for the sampling strategy, and if so, how many choices should be present?

Some workers complain about the duplication of one row and column with the adjacent tile, but this is just an implementation decision that adds minimally to the size of the DEM and is handled transparently by software. They also complain that the contributing area for edge pixels lies “outside the DEM”, but this is only a matter of interpreting the file name (which only includes a corner by convention) or the metadata. Equally valid would be to consider the pixel centroids, which many software programs use for all computations.

VII. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work would not have been possible without countless contributions from my DEMIX colleagues. This paper underwent minor additions after the Perugia conference to reflect discussions there.

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